

**Slovak Society of Chemical Engineering
Institute of Chemical and Environmental Engineering
Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava**

PROCEEDINGS

44th International Conference of the Slovak Society of Chemical Engineering

Hotel SNP

Demänovská dolina, Low Tatras, Slovakia

May 22–26, 2017

Editors: Dr. Marek Blahušiak, Dr. Mário Mihaľ

ISBN: 978-80-89597-58-1, EAN: 9788089597581

Plachá, M., Kočí, P., Novák, V.: Development of lattice boltzmann model for flow in porous filters, Editors: Blahušiak, M., Mihaľ, M., In *44th International Conference of the Slovak Society of Chemical Engineering*, Demänovská dolina, Slovakia, 310–319, 2017.

Development of Lattice Boltzmann model for flow in porous filters

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Key words: Lattice Boltzmann method, fluid flow, 3D reconstruction

Introduction

The pollution reduction is one of the main tasks in automotive industry thus new technologies in automotive exhaust gas aftertreatment are being developed. There are four main pollutants which are legislatively restricted: CO, NO_x, hydrocarbons and soot particles. The gaseous pollutants are converted to non-toxic products in catalytic monoliths and the particles are removed in a particulate filter. Until recently, only Diesel engines were fitted with filters because they produce larger quantities of bigger and heavier soot particles in comparison with gasoline engine. However, it has been found out that the small particles, below 100 nm, are present in high numbers but they contribute only a little to the total mass. While relatively small number of the larger particles dominates the particulate mass [1], it has been reported that it is the smaller particles that are proposed to be the most harmful to human health [2]. Therefore, new emission standards focus not only on the mass of particles occurring in exhaust gas, but also on their number. Even gasoline engines do not fulfil the upcoming emission legislation and they will have to be fitted with a particulate filter.

Figure 1: An example of a particulate filter.

Both automotive catalytic converters and particulate filters are monolith reactors composed of a system of parallel channels. Converters are flow-through (channels open at both ends) and their walls are coated with an active layer. In contrast, the channels of particulate filters are blocked at one end which forces gas to flow through porous wall, Figure 1. The upcoming legislation requires that both systems will have to be present in every car to meet the emission limits. Therefore, the current future development is focused on the combination of porous filter

and catalyst in one monolith reactor. This set up reduces size and weight of the exhaust gas aftertreatment system. However, the combined system can negatively affect permeability, pressure drop and reactant conversion. The system can thus fail to meet the emission limits if it is poorly designed. The gas transport in a coated filter can be studied experimentally as well as with the help of mathematical modelling. Three main modelling approaches to simulation of gas flow can be identified, Figure 2. On the macroscopic scale, the transport phenomena can be described by Navier-Stokes equations (NS) which work with macroscopic velocity. On the other hand, molecular dynamics method considers velocity of every particle in a medium. The Lattice Boltzmann method (LBM) is somewhere in between those two methods. This method works with statistical variables representing a set of particles.

Figure 2: Three main approaches to the modelling of gas flow [3]

Implementation of Lattice Boltzmann method

Lattice Boltzmann method can be used for solving different problems as diffusion, isothermal or non-isothermal incompressible Navier-Stokes equations [4]. Gas flow through a porous structure can be simulated as isothermal incompressible flow due to low Mach number (<0.3) of the flow. The Navier-Stokes equations for incompressible flow can be recovered from Lattice Boltzmann method can be used to solve gas flow through a porous structure. The derivation of Navier-Stokes equations from Lattice Boltzmann has been first proven on a hexagonal lattice by U. Frish et al. [5]. In the following sections, simplified derivation of Lattice Boltzmann equation and its transformation into Navier-Stokes equations is introduced.

Lattice Boltzmann equation

Lattice Boltzmann method is based on lattice gas automata which is a kinetic model with discrete lattice, time and particle velocities. Particles in lattice gas automata can move around, but only within lattice nodes. Lattice Boltzmann method work with the distribution function $f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{e}, t)$ which statistically describes a system behaviour. The function $f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{e}, t)$ represents the number of gas molecules at a time t positioned between \mathbf{x} and $\mathbf{x} + d\mathbf{x}$ which have velocities in an interval $\mathbf{e}, \mathbf{e} + d\mathbf{e}$.

After discretisation, non-dimensionalisation and other mathematical adjustments, Lattice Boltzmann equation (1) can be derived. $F_i(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{e}_i \Delta t, t + \Delta t)$ is discretised distribution function with time step Δt and space step $\Delta \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{e}_i \Delta t$, where \mathbf{e}_i is lattice velocity [6].

$$F_i(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{e}_i \Delta t, t + \Delta t) - F_i(\mathbf{x}, t) = -\frac{1}{\tau} (F_i - F_i^{eq}) \quad (1)$$

The equation (1) can be solved in two sequential steps:

1. Collision: incoming fluid particles at a particular node change their velocity directions according to the scattering rules. Collisions are considered as relaxation towards a local equilibrium.
2. Streaming: each particles moves to the nearest node in the directions of their velocities [7].

This approach is easy to implement and it can be applied for a variety of different problems such as mass, momentum and heat diffusion etc. The equation for different problems differs by choosing different lattice arrangement, equilibrium distribution function and source term.

Lattice arrangement

Lattice arrangements differ in number of dimensions and number of linkages. Several lattice arrangements have been introduced over the years. The lattices used in this work are D2Q9 (two dimensional with nine linkages), Figure 3 and D3Q19 (three dimensional with nineteen linkages), Figure 4. This lattices have been proven to be stable and suitable for isothermal incompressible fluid flow which is used as approximation for flow through porous media [8]. Position in lattice is described by lattice velocities \mathbf{e}_i which are summarised as column vectors in matrixes $E2$ and $E3$, respectively. The order and value of velocities has been chosen in order to simplify the FORTRAN code.

$$E2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$E3 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Figure 3: Lattice arrangement of D2Q9 with velocities e .

Figure 4: Lattice arrangement of D3Q19 with velocities e .

Macroscopic quantities

The distribution functions are linked with macroscopic mass density ρ and velocity \mathbf{u} by equations (4) and (5), where M is the number of neighbouring nodes, equal to 9 and 19 for chosen lattice arrangements.

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{i=1}^M F_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{1}{\rho(\mathbf{x}, t)} \sum_{i=1}^M F_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{e}_i \quad (5)$$

Equilibrium distribution function

The equilibrium distribution function $F_i^{(eq)}$ used for isothermal incompressible fluid flow is an expansion of Maxwell's distribution function for low Mach number ($Ma \ll 0.3$). The equilibrium distribution function is then expressed by equation (6), where w_i is global equilibrium distribution varying for different lattice arrangements. The complied derivation of this equation can be found in [9].

$$F_i^{(eq)}(\rho, \mathbf{u}) = w_i \rho \left[1 + 3(\mathbf{e}_i \cdot \mathbf{u}) - \frac{3}{2} \mathbf{u}^2 + \frac{9}{2} (\mathbf{e}_i \cdot \mathbf{u})^2 \right] \quad (6)$$

Lattice Boltzmann to Navier-Stokes equation

Incompressible Navier-Stokes equation can be obtained from the previous equation by applying the Chapman-Enskog expansion (multi-scale technique) as described in [6]. Both equations are in Lattice Boltzmann variables (index LB). The conversion from real to lattice Boltzmann variables can be found in [10].

$$\nabla_{LB} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{LB} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\partial_{t_{LB}} \mathbf{u}_{LB} + (\mathbf{u}_{LB} \cdot \nabla_{LB}) \mathbf{u}_{LB} = -\nabla_{LB} p_{LB} + \nu_{LB} \nabla_{LB}^2 \mathbf{u}_{LB} \quad (8)$$

Lattice pressure $p_{LB} = \rho_{LB} \frac{k_B T}{m} = \frac{\rho_{LB}}{3}$ and lattice viscosity $\nu_{LB} = \frac{1}{3} \left(\tau - \frac{1}{2} \right)$.

Boundary conditions

Implementing right boundary condition is one of the most difficult tasks in mathematical modelling. Over the years, different boundary conditions have been introduced. This paper focus only on the most common boundary conditions for Lattice Boltzmann models such as no-slip condition, periodic boundaries, zero flux and constant velocity boundaries.

1. No-slip boundary condition

No-slip boundary condition also known as bounce-back boundary is used on the solid-fluid interface. The method implies that an incoming particle towards the solid wall bounces back into fluid flow. This is achieved by inverting the distribution functions F_i as shown in Figure 5. The bounce-back scheme is known as on-grid bounce-back. The distribution functions are returned to fluid on the wall nodes. The scheme is easy to implement and achieves first order accuracy. Furthermore, it does not need any special care in corner nodes which makes it ideal for complex geometries such as porous media [11].

Figure 5: Illustration of on-grid no-slip boundary condition [12].

2. Periodic boundary

Another commonly used boundary condition is periodic boundary. It is easy to implement them and thus simulate the infinitely large medium in an applied direction. Implementation in LBM is achieved by copying the distribution functions F_i from one side to the other one. In contrary to other methods, e.g. Finite element method, does not require a periodic structure.

3. Zero flux boundary

The zero flux boundary is commonly used in mathematical modelling of fluid flow. Unfortunately, this boundary condition cannot be imposed by simply copying the last but one values into the last one. This approach can lead to backward propagation disturbances and instabilities [11]. Possible solution of this problem is to use of the same bounce back boundary condition as for solid-fluid boundary.

4. Constant velocity boundaries

Inlet and outlet boundary is in this work achieved by implementing a constant flow (constant velocity). This boundary condition was derived in [13]. The key is to compute unknown distribution function on the boundary from known velocity. In addition, the derivation depends on the position of the boundary.

Results

Three case studies are presented in this section in order to validate and demonstrate the developed 2D and 3D LBM models. The cases include a laminar flow in a pipe, flow around an obstacle and flow in a pore structure.

Poiseuille flow

First case study is a laminar fluid flow between two walls known as Poiseuille flow. Air at 100 °C has been chosen as a medium in this simulations. Fluid flow is driven by a pressure difference. Goal of the simulation is to calculate velocity profile in a pipe and compare it to its analytical solution. Analytical solution is derived from simplified incompressible Navier-Stokes equation and the final form is in equation (9), where u_{in} is inlet velocity set as a boundary condition.

$$u_y = 6 u_{in} \frac{x}{D^2} (D - x) \quad (9)$$

The comparison of both 2D and 3D models to analytical solution can be seen in Figure 6. The predicted velocity is similar for both models, with the same error against analytical solution. The influence of two different discretisations is presented only for 2D model in Figure 7. As expected, higher discretisation shows more accurate prediction near the wall. It is also expressed by a lower error showed in Figure 8. Although, an error about 50% from the analytical solution is observed in a point next to the wall it then rapidly decreases. It might indicate that even higher discretisation is needed in a close vicinity of the wall. Both discretisations show similar error about 4% in the centre of the pipe.

Figure 6: Comparison of velocity profile obtained from 2D and 3D model.

Inlet velocity set to 0.5 m/s and $Re = 22$

Figure 7: Velocity profile form 2D model for different discretisation in the same cross-section.

Inlet velocity set to 0.5 m/s and $Re = 22$

Figure 8: Absolute error of 2D velocity against analytical solution. Inlet velocity set to 0.5 m/s and $Re = 22$

Flow passing an obstacle

Flow pass an obstacle has been chosen as other case study to evaluate developed models. Flow passing an obstacle is an important process commonly occurring in porous media. The aim here is to predict von Kármán’s vortexes that start to develop at Reynolds number close to 100. Air at 100 °C has been chosen as a medium also in this simulations. Two values of inlet velocity (0.5 and 10 m/s) have been chosen for the simulation, which lead to Reynolds number 4 and 86, respectively. The flow passing an obstacle at Reynolds number 4 is laminar and no vortexes are present as expected, Figure 9. The start of vortex formation can be seen in Figure 10, where the Reynolds number is 86. The 3D model shows analogical behaviour.

Figure 9: Velocity profile (m/s) of flow passing an obstacle.
 Inlet velocity 0.5 m/s, $D = 0.2$ mm, $Re = 4$, $t = 0-0.025$ s

Figure 10: Velocity profile (m/s) of flow passing an obstacle.
 Inlet velocity 10 m/s, $D = 0.2$ mm, $Re = 86$ at $t = 0-0.025$ s.

Flow in porous media

Last case study has been chosen a fluid model in a porous structure. The 2D model has been briefly tested on randomly generated structures with water at 20 °C as fluid. Periodic boundary condition has been used in the x-direction. The results proven to be in an agreement with known fluid patterns, Figure 11. The 3D model has been tested on reconstructed porous filters. The 3D images of porous filter wall has been obtained from X-ray microtomography and processed into a 3D structure matrix which was directly used in developed model. Air at 20 °C has been chosen as a medium in this type of simulations. The example of a flow in a 3D porous structure can be seen in Figure 12. Zero flux boundary conditions are applied on the x and z direction in this simulations. The 3D model was tested on four different porous filters with different porosities. The calculated pressure drop and permeability from the presented Lattice Boltzmann method are summarised in Table 1.

Figure 11: Velocity profile of flow through 2D porous medium with porosity $\varepsilon = 80 \%$. Inlet velocity 1 m/s.

Figure 12: Velocity profile in 3D reconstructed SiC porous filter. Inlet velocity 0.1 m/s.

Table 1: Macroporosity ε , pressure drop over a length $\frac{dp}{dy}$ and permeability μ evaluated for four different porous filters.

Sample ID	ε (1)	$\frac{dp}{dy}$ (bar/m)	μ (m ²)
Cordierite	0.65	1.18	8.78×10^{-6}
SCRF bare	0.58	1.23	7.66×10^{-6}
SiC-narrow pores	0.47	2.68	6.18×10^{-6}
SiC-wide pores	0.45	1.46	4.87×10^{-6}

Conclusion

In this work, spatially 2D and 3D Lattice Boltzmann models of a fluid flow has been newly developed. The models were shown to predict correctly the developing velocity profiles between two walls known as Poiseuille flow. The 2D model is able to simulate also a flow around an obstacle, including the formation of von Kármán's vortexes. Both models can also predict the velocity profile and pressure drop in porous media. The 3D model has successfully calculated pressure drop and permeability in a 3D reconstructed porous structures.

Acknowledgements

The results were developed within the project PARTIAL-PGMs GA No. 686086 supported in the frame of EU program Horizon 2020.

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